

From classroom to practice sites: A correlation study of the student's academic performance in hospital pharmacy internship subject vs their practical performance on actual internship site

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Abstract

The transition from classroom-based instruction to hands-on clinical training is a key factor in the competencies of pharmacy students, especially in hospital settings where technical and clinical skills are important. The COVID-19 pandemic presented significant challenges in presenting online instruction to the actual hospital pharmacy work such as inventory of medications, disposal of expired/used medication, temperature monitoring, compounding practice, medication reconciliation, oncology pharmacy processes and workflow, satellite pharmacy, unit dose delivery system, and infection prevention and control due to limitations on facilities and equipment. This research study determined the correlation between the academic performance of fourth year students in a hospital pharmacy internship lecture course and their practical performance during clinical internship rotations, as evaluated by their preceptors. The study used a quantitative, non-experimental approach with all 16 students involved. Results showed a moderate to strong positive association ($r = 0.53$, $p = 0.011$) between academic performance in the internship course and evaluations from preceptors during clinical training. The findings highlight the importance of combining academic learning with structured practice sessions to help students be better prepared for real-world pharmacy work.

Keywords: Academic performance; Practical performance; Clinical performance; Internship; Pharmacy course.

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Introduction

Pharmacy is a profession that changes quickly and connects scientific knowledge with direct care for patients (Koehler & Brown, 2017). In the past, pharmacists mainly focused on dispensing medications and keeping track of inventory. But in recent years, their job has grown to include helping patients with their medications, giving them advice, and working with other healthcare professionals as part of a team (Babiker et al., 2014). With these new responsibilities, pharmacists help improve how treatments work, help patients follow their medication plans, and make healthcare a better quality (Rajiah et al., 2021).

To develop these skills, students need a structured education that blends classroom learning with real-world experience. Classroom-based courses teach the basics of drugs, how hospitals operate, and how the pharmaceutical system works. Internships and clinical training, on the other hand, allow students experience the challenges of real practice, such as making sterile medicines, checking medication lists, and following infection control regulations (Revolinski et al., 2020). These hands-on experiences are key to helping students move from being good in class to being skilled in practice.

The COVID-19 pandemic changed this setup by pushing many pharmacy programs to use online or virtual instruction (Higbea et al., 2021). While online learning is effective in promoting new ideas, it is not as effective for teaching skills, especially in areas such as hospital pharmacy internships where hands-on practice is necessary (Lee & Vermillion, 2018). Because of this, there has been concern to whether how students attend virtual classes might not reflect how they could perform in real hospital settings (Compton et al., 2020).

Research in other healthcare fields shows mixed findings. Some studies suggest that strong academic performance is a good indicator for clinical success (Buhat-Mendoza et al., 2014; Velayo et al., 2014), while others focus on non-academic qualities such as communication, flexibility, and teamwork (Berduzco-Torres et al., 2021; Patterson et al., 2019). For pharmacy education, there is not much research, especially in areas affected by pandemic changes. This study attempts to fill the gap by determining the correlation between academic performance in a hospital pharmacy internship subject and practical performance in actual hospital internship sites among fourth-year pharmacy students.

Figure 1. Research framework

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized a quantitative non-experimental correlational design that describes social phenomena but does not include manipulation from an independent variable. A correlational design focuses on the relationships between variables without controlling or manipulating them (Curtis et al., 2016). This research design usually ends with either positive or negative.

Participants and Sampling

The study population included 16 fourth-year pharmacy students at St. Dominic College of Asia who were taking part in the hospital pharmacy internship program during the second semester of the academic year 2021–2022. Every student was included in the study, so that their performance would not be missed. This method thereby avoided any bias in selecting participants and made the results more accurate (Lash et al., 2014).

Data Collection

Two sets of information were gathered:

Academic performance – grades students received in the hospital pharmacy internship lecture course, which was based on the average of their scores from the preliminary and midterm examination scores.

Clinical performance – scores given by experienced pharmacists who were supervising the students at the hospitals where they did their internships.

These evaluations were done using standardized rubrics that checked their practical skills, professionalism, and task completion in actual hospital settings.

Data Analysis

Pearson’s correlation coefficient was used to see how closely academic and clinical performances were related with each other. The results were considered significant if the level of confidence was higher than 95% (0.05 alpha level).

Results

Table 1. Academic and clinical performance of students during the hospital pharmacy internship

Student	Prelim Grade	Midterm Grade	Instructor Evaluation from Classroom Lecture (Average of Prelim and Midterm Grade)	Preceptor Evaluation from Hospital Internship Site
Student 1	85.61	87.37	86.49	85.25
Student 2	86.19	84.80	85.50	93.5
Student 3	88.09	89.84	88.97	97
Student 4	90.77	85.76	88.27	94.75
Student 5	78.96	85.37	82.17	96
Student 6	83.86	90.47	87.17	97
Student 7	85.13	88.33	86.73	97.75
Student 8	88.37	87.92	88.15	97.25
Student 9	81.22	87.66	84.44	95.25
Student 10	86.93	85.04	85.99	97
Student 11	88.65	90.34	89.50	97.75
Student 12	89.05	88.66	88.86	97.25
Student 13	86.22	87.96	87.09	95.25
Student 14	75.70	81.57	78.64	85
Student 15	80.19	88.16	84.18	97.75

Table 1 shows both the academic and clinical performance of students during the hospital pharmacy internship. Their academic performance is measured by their average scores on the prelim and midterm exams in the lecture class, while their clinical performance is assessed by the preceptors at the hospital.

The academic scores varied from 75.70 to 90.77, showing that students had different levels of success in classroom-based tests. On the other hand, clinical scores were generally higher, ranging from 85.00 to 97.75, with most students scoring above 95. This suggests that preceptors might have given more positive evaluations, or that the hospital setting allowed students to show skills that were not elaborated in the virtual classroom.

High-performing students in academics also usually did stronger in clinical work. For example, Student 11 had one of the highest academic averages (89.50) and also got the highest clinical score (97.75). Student 3 also did well in both areas—academic (88.97) and clinical (97.00). These examples show that their academic knowledge often helps when applying this into real-life situations.

However, some students had different results in their academic and clinical work. Student 5 had an average academic score of 82.17 but scored very high in clinical training (96.00), showing that some students may learn better through hands-on experience than through exams. Student 14, on the other hand, had the lowest academic score (78.64) and also got a low clinical rating (85.00), which fits the pattern that weaker academic performance might mean less readiness for clinical work. While most students performed

well in both academic and clinical areas, some exceptions show that other factors such as adaptability, professionalism, and communication skills play a role in clinical success.

Table 2. Statistical analysis between instructor and preceptor evaluations

Statistical Tool	Result
Coefficient (r)	0.530089
N	17
T-statistic	2.1314
DF	16
p-value	0.011

Table 2 shows the statistical relationship between academic and clinical performance. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.53$) suggests a moderate to strong positive relationship. This means students who scored higher in their academics usually also got higher ratings from their preceptors.

The result was statistically significant ($p = 0.011 < 0.05$), which means there is a strong connection between academic performance and clinical performance. However, since the correlation is only moderate, academic performance alone does not fully predict clinical success. Other factors such as communication skills, problem-solving, adaptability, and professionalism also play a big role in how preceptors evaluate students.

The analysis also found some students who performed better clinically than expected, even with average academic scores, such as Student 5 and Student 15. These cases show that academic scores, while important, might not capture all the strengths students bring to real-life clinical situations.

Discussion

The study shows that academic performance, as judged by clinical instructors, is connected to clinical performance, as judged by hospital preceptors. The results show a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.53$, $p = 0.011$), meaning that academic success helps students be better in their clinical work during pharmacy internships.

This matches other research studies found in health education. For example, Carr et al. (2014) found that students who did well in class also did better in their jobs. Similarly, Lee and Vermillion (2018) discovered how students did in medical school was linked to their internships. However, the correlation is not very strong, which means that while academic performance is essential, it is not the only factor that influences clinical success. Clinical settings require more than just knowing theory; thus, they need skills such as communicating with people, being flexible, working with others, and being professional (Rogers et al., 2010). Students like Student 5 and Student 15, who did not perform very well in academics but excelled in practice, show how important these non-academic skills are.

Also, it seems that hospital supervisors give higher scores than teachers do, which might be because on some differences in assessment focus. Teachers look at understanding theory and mastering knowledge on tests, while supervisors look at how well students apply knowledge, solve problems in real situations, and behave professionally. This means that academic and clinical performance are related, but they measure different things.

The COVID-19 pandemic made it more complex to balance classroom learning with hands-on experience. With fewer chances to practice, school performance became the main way to measure competence during online learning (Alotaibi, 2016). Yet, preceptors still saw many students applying their knowledge effectively in real-world settings, which shows that pharmacy education is resilient. To help students better connect school and clinical work, programs should include simulation training, case studies, and hybrid learning methods that combine classroom and clinical experiences (Arigbede et al., 2014; Tsai

et al., 2015). This study shows that academic performance is significant but not the whole predictor for clinical success. To prepare students for real pharmacy work, it is important to build strong academic skills and give them chances to develop applied skills in real or simulated clinical situations.

Conclusion

This study showed that students' grades in the hospital pharmacy internship lecture course were closely correlated with their clinical performance during their hospital internship. Students who got better grades in class usually got better scores in their clinical work, which means doing well in class can help predict their practice readiness in real-world settings.

However, the study also found that the correlation was moderate, meaning other factors such as adaptability, communication, professionalism, and hands-on skills play a role in the clinical success of the student. Some students did better in the hospital than their grades suggested, showing how important real-life experience is in pharmacy training.

Pharmacy programs should keep improving their classroom teaching and add more simulation-based training, hands-on activities, and learning methods that mix theory with practice. In this way, future pharmacists will not only do well in school but also be ready to provide good care and show strong professional skills in real healthcare settings.

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